

ВЛИЯНИЕ ПРИРОДЫ КАТАЛИЗАТОРА И ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ НА УХОД ПРОДУКТА В РЕАКЦИИ АМИНОМЕТИЛИРОВАНИЯ

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Аннотация: *Роль различных катализаторов в реакциях аминометилирования органических веществ. Каталитические свойства солей меди в реакциях аминометилирования. Отличие скорости реакции в зависимости от солей.*

Ключевые слова: *анализ, альдегиды, мономеры, фармакологический, мономеры, амиды, аминометилирование*

INFLUENCE OF THE NATURE OF THE CATALYST ON THE CARE OF THE PRODUCT IN THE AMINOMETHYLATION REACTION

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Abstract: *Different catalysts play an important role in the amino methylation reactions of organic substances. The catalytic properties are important in the aminomethylation reactions of copper salts. The reaction rate varies in different salts.*

Keywords: *analysis, aldehydes, monomers, pharmacological, monomers, amides, aminomethylation*

The synthesis of hydroxy, carboxy and sulfoxy derivatives based on certain monomers, amides, amines and aldehydes by converting saturated hydrocarbons into

unsaturated states has long been known [1, p. 7] The synthesis of hydroxy, carboxy and sulfoxy derivatives of pharmacological compounds based on unsaturated monomers, amides, amines and aldehydes has well-known functional groups, which remain important drugs in applied medicine. Since many amine derivatives have a wide range of therapeutic effects and low toxicity, the synthesis and study of new compounds is important. However, few systematic studies are currently underway to study the properties of the factors affecting the synthesis process, and the range of action of catalysts is very large [2, p. 64]. Synthesis of hydroxy-, carboxy and sulfoxy derivatives based on special monomers, amides, amines and aldehydes by transferring saturated hydrocarbons to an unsaturated state. Polymers, elastomers with nanostructures, the study of their physicochemical and operational properties, the creation of technologies for obtaining products with a given structure and properties is directed for scientific research.

Based on the analysis of the literature, we carried out the reaction aminomethylation of acetylenic alcohol, the reaction proceeds according to the following scheme.

Synthesis of hydroxy-, carboxy and sulfoxy derivatives based on special monomers, amides, amines and aldehydes by converting saturated hydrocarbons into an unsaturated state [3, p. 23]. Polymers, elastomers with nanostructures The study of their physical, chemical and operational properties, the creation of technologies for obtaining products with a given structure and properties is aimed at scientific research according to the scheme. $\text{CuSO}_4 > (\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2\text{Cu} > \text{AgNO}_3 > \text{CuCl} > \text{CuCl}_2 > \text{CuBr} > \text{CuBr}_2 > \text{CuJ}$

Influence of the nature of the catalyst on the product yield in the aminomethylation reaction

catalyst composition	Unum , %							
	Wit h uJ	CuBr 2	CuB r	CuCl ₂	CuCl	AgNO ₃	(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Cu	CuSO ₄
HO CH ₂ -C≡C-CH ₂ -N	35.7	37.42	39.4 0	40.20	47.6	51.4	66.25	74.6
HO CH ₂ -C≡C-CH ₂ -N	37.1	41.75	42.1	43.4	46.6	49.3	67.4	78.4
HO CH ₂ -C≡C-CH ₂ -N	47.7	49.2	53.4	55.2	57.4	61.6	69.5	75.6
HO CH ₂ -C≡C-CH ₂ -N	44.3	45.1	47.8	49.5	53.6	60.4	75.4	80.6

In conclusion, many copper salts in the reaction have been tested as catalysts. The lowest result was obtained in the synthesis of 4-N diethylamino-butyn-2-ol-1 on a catalyst from copper iodide salt. It was found that the catalytic properties between two copper salts of copper sulfate are very high [4, p. 47]. A number of measures are being taken in the country to process natural gas, obtain monomers, liquid organic compounds, biologically active substances and their derivatives, and use products in the chemical industry and agriculture. Deep processing of resources, accelerating the production of finished products. , development of new types of products and technologies [5, p. 62]. In this regard, scientific research aimed at studying inhibitors synthesized on the basis of propargyl alcohol and secondary amines containing mobile hydrogen and due to three bonds is of great importance. General information about the aminomethylation reaction and its products is given in foreign and domestic scientific literature [6, p. 37]. . It has been reported that multi-step reactions reduce the yield of the final product. Based on this, we carried out the reaction of aminomethylation of acetylenic alcohol, which proceeds according to the following scheme.

In the aminomethylation of acetylenic alcohol, the choice of the temperature of the reaction medium is important. When the temperature rises to 40 oC, the reaction rate is low, at 40-90 oC the yield is 10-15%, at 95-100°C the yield of aminomethylation is 66%. However, when the temperature exceeds 100°C, the product yield decreases.

1-4 (N-piperidino)butine-2-ol-1;

2-4 (N,N¹-diallylo)butin -2 -ol -1];

3-4 (N,N¹- diisobutyl) butin -2 - ol -1.

Experiments have shown that in aminomethylation reactions , in order to achieve the expected synthesis of a substance, a high yield of the product, it is important to make the optimal choice of temperature and catalyst.

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